

ART

THE "COMMONALITY" AND "DIVERSITY" OF THE IMPROVISED ELEMENTS IN WESTERN ORCHESTRAL MUSIC

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Abstract

For Western orchestral music, it not only plays an indispensable role in the world music field, but also because of its strong blending characteristics, improvisation elements are used by performers in their daily lives or performance activities. In fact, improvisation elements belong to local residents in a certain region or improvised tunes or lyrics created by Western orchestral performers based on the on-site atmosphere. This article will explore the commonalities and diversity in the improvisation components of Western orchestral music, focusing on the beauty of improvisation and the control of vocal singing style.

Keywords: Western orchestral music; Commonality; Diversity; Instrumental performance.

Introduction:

Generally speaking, in the historical evolution of Western orchestral music performance works, musicologists often place more emphasis on the composition part of the content, rather than focusing on the improvisation process before the work is completed. Later, due to the continuous development of the foundation of civilization, it was not until then that the completed music was subjected to in-depth analysis. Regarding the content of vocal music, it is required to master the correct and scientific singing techniques. Singing techniques, as various techniques to showcase style, require learners to have a profound understanding of the relationship between singing techniques and style in vocal music teaching.

1. Development status

For the improvisation component in Western orchestral music, there is currently not much research that can be used as a reference. Tracing back to the long history of the world, only one musicologist has put great effort into studying improvisation music. This pure researcher is Ernst Froude, who also wrote the book "Improvisation in Music" about improvisation music. Since then, It was not until the mid-1960s that improvisational music achieved relatively stable development driven by the development of jazz.

In the latter half of the last century, the concept of improvisation music had a significant impact on the formation of Western orchestral music in West Asia, Southeast Asia, and South Asia. Although improvisation music has developed, its position in the field of Western orchestral music in the world is still very small. We need to understand that improvisation music has not been extensively studied as a separate module by Western orchestral musicians around the world for a long time. The main reason behind this phenomenon is that improvisation music is widely distributed in Western orchestral music, but it has not been fully understood and recognized. This status makes it even rarer for people to devote themselves to studying it, The reason why Western orchestral music can develop in modern society is because the widespread activities of Western orchestral societies and the gradual relaxation

of the social environment have led to a unique path of diversification in the creation and development of music genres. From this, it can be seen that the development of improvisation music will gradually highlight its own social value and characteristics in the development of Western orchestral music around the world.

2. Inheritance requirements

In the Western music system, impromptu music is usually regarded as "third world music", and most musicologists and musicologists use it as a means and concept, such as non Western music or jazz. From historical records, there are few traces of Western orchestral improvisation music in the history of art and music, and most of them remain in the interpretation and description of Western orchestral improvisation music. This vague feature often shares the same beauty as the fantasies of famous artists such as Chopin, Schubert, and Mozart, while also possessing the ambiguity of musical structure.

From the perspective of art and music, the meaning of improvisation lies in the fact that it was formed without precise planning and planning, which represents music creation without prior preparation or basic music technology. Compared to white musicians, the authenticity and appeal of improvisation music with colored Western orchestras are stronger, because improvisation musicians often need to create imaginative music works in an instant, Improvisation writers are not bound by norms and have a strong desire for freedom.

Improvisation music is not a primary form of artistic inheritance in the field of Western art and music, but rather a relatively minor form of inheritance. However, its development in West Asia and South Asia is vastly different from its development in the field of Western art and music, and it can even be said to completely overturn it. The most popular and widely circulated form in West Asia and South Asia is improvisation music, The ones that are loved by many are often improvised music that lacks regularity and rhythm. In these regions, relatively speaking, music created through prior preparation does not enjoy the same status as improvised music.

Although there is the above historical situation, overall, from the perspective of the development history of Western orchestral music in the world, improvisational music and other types of music have equal status, and the complexity and normative characteristics in improvisational music have also had a significant impact on performance [2]. For example, in Indian improvisation music, there are special procedural norms that require organists to perform with unique style requirements, as well as various requirements for language, education, diversity, and social aspects of jazz in the current environment. More importantly, improvisation music has a distinct understanding of emotional expression compared to other music, with emotional factors greatly exceeding rational factors. In summary, improvisation music is both unique and important in the world of Western orchestral music, and its position is indispensable. However, based on the current development situation, it still needs to undergo long-term inheritance and development, and the free and uncontrolled music style conveyed by it is also unique.

3. Aesthetic and Singing Commonalities

(1) Aesthetics

For example, from the perspective of improvisation, taking the erhu performance as an example, we can find that the beauty of improvisation music mainly lies in the following three aspects, namely the changes in tone, flower playing, and gradual rhythm.

Firstly, in terms of vocal changes, it is necessary for the performer to improvise in detail based on the composition of the vocal itself. The same note may also have different emotions due to the performer's different needs and understanding. The performer can handle the strength and treble of the instrument according to the specific environment, thereby showcasing the beauty of improvised music [3].

Secondly, for the performance of adding flowers, it refers to the decorative processing of subtracting and adding notes on the original melody, using decorative notes to set off the rising and falling notes of the phrases using color techniques, in order to showcase the tonal personality and charm of erhu instruments.

Finally, the content of gradients should be explored from the perspective of the player's level of control over gradients, which is closely related to the player's musical style. Typically, the player controls the speed of acute gradients based on their own understanding of the music.

(2) Common singing techniques

The first requirement for understanding the commonality of singing is to have a keen perception ability, be able to make corresponding judgments based on the skills, behaviors, and subtle changes in sound form in singing, and mobilize various senses to collaborate and participate. The most crucial aspect is hearing, and a thorough study of vocal phenomena can make accurate judgments in a timely manner. Secondly, it is necessary to uncover and understand the mechanism of human musical instruments based on their vocal ability and foundation, fully understand acoustic theory, and thus tap into the potential of human musical instruments, enabling them to achieve sustainable development. The

focus is on consciously adjusting and arranging the various steps in the human voice with priority, division of labor, and layout, in order to ensure that the audience can feel the movement and relaxation during the singing process.

4. Commonality

In the process of studying a small number of Western orchestral music in our country, we often encounter improvisational elements in Western orchestral music. We can see that the Aken singers of the Kirgiz ethnic group use improvisational singing. Aken singers create music based on the state and situation of the scene, mainly using the instrument Kumzi for accompaniment, while the singer plays specific lyrics in the music accompaniment, for folk artists, such performance forms often do not have specific rules and regulations.

However, compared to the Western music system, a few Western orchestral music in our country are vastly different. In the improvisation of Western orchestral music, some folk compositions from oral culture are basically the same as those from written culture, and the parts for modification and creation need to be prepared in advance, with corresponding systematic methods and modes. It can be said that the improvisation of Western orchestral music in the Western music system was also inspired by inspiration, but it also operates according to corresponding rules and needs to be processed and rearranged for specific music vocabulary and units. So from another perspective, improvisation and composition exist as two different forms of expression of the same thing. For example, in the improvisational tunes of the Kazakh Aytes, theories from the Western music system can be used to classify the modes and tonality. They can be specifically divided into Do mode and la mode categories. The Do mode category includes pentatonic scale, hexatonic scale, walking scale, and octatonic scale, while the la mode category includes six tone scale and walking scale, while the recitation type improvisational tunes adopt an 11 syllable poetic structure, The improvisational melody of singing generally adopts an 8-syllable poetic structure.

Relatively speaking, from the above situation, we can see that in the eyes of ordinary people, spontaneous and casual improvisation performances also have a certain pattern. In terms of the creative process of music, most music has a certain fixed pattern and does not apply improvisation components to a large proportion. Therefore, it can be seen that the content presented by improvisation components in Western orchestral music in objective modes should be explored from two aspects. One is to find a fixed pattern for improvisation performance, Another aspect is to learn about various ways of improvisation.

For music creators, the composition units and usage principles of music may change due to cultural differences, with certain differences in quantity and nature. The existing objective template research on the improvisation components of Western orchestral music is generally based on the composition theory, performance theory, and improvisation theory analyzed from the Western music system. Essentially, this set of theo-

ries is based on the research perspective of Western music theory and may not be applicable to all Western orchestral music. Since the early 20th century, people around the world have also gained a basic understanding of this and can understand that in certain situations, patterns in music cannot be applied to each other.

5. Diversity

All Western orchestral music has its own music, and each has its own cultural characteristics. The constantly changing musical units in the music also exist as the rhythm structure of many Western orchestral music. Therefore, it can be seen that the commonalities between Western orchestral improvisational music are ubiquitous. However, the music system between each Western orchestra is also independent, as the development of social environments has led to a richer diversity in Western orchestra music. These diversity are closely related to the work and life of local residents, as well as the history and culture. Therefore, the diversity reflected in Western orchestra music also reflects the diversity of Western orchestra to a certain extent.

The diversity of improvisational music mainly lies in the differences in the development process of Western orchestral music. For example, for the Kazakh people in nomadic Western orchestras, improvisation in music is mainly generated during the competition for property among the Kazakh ethnic group. Therefore, the content of competitive elements can be clearly felt in the improvisation of the Kazakh people. The lyrics in Aytes do not have significant intonation fluctuations, and the speaking speed is relatively fast, This is similar to the arguments and reasoning that arise in the process of safeguarding interests in daily life, and the lyrics are paired with a melody that is flat but fast-paced. Because in the process of historical development and evolution, the time for ethnic groups to compete for property has gradually disappeared, but the improvised music left behind has become a historical relic of Kazakh Western orchestral culture, fully demonstrating the historical background and appearance of nomadic Western orchestral culture, and thus fully proving that the diversity of Western orchestral culture and history has played a decisive role in the diversity of Western orchestral music.

In many Western orchestral music, there is a phenomenon of hierarchical classification, such as classical Chinese music and Indian folk music. Moreover, due to cultural and historical reasons, the standards for evaluating the level of musicians and the appreciation needs of music performances in various Western orchestral cultures will also change during different periods of historical development. On the basis of the development of commodity economy and social productivity, the music culture of the Song Dynasty in China began to shift from the mainstream state of palace aristocratic music to a situation where music was mainly enjoyed by the citizen class. The popular music of the Song Dynasty's citizen class had the characteristics of enthusiasm, unrestrained and straightforward, and was closely related to life. The development of traditional Chinese opera was a typical representative of popular music among the citizens of the Song Dynasty. Through the absorption of various folk cultures and the

reference of folk life stories, traditional Chinese opera gradually developed from original comical dramas into mature dramas, ushering in the era of traditional Chinese opera music. When traditional Chinese opera music spreads on the streets and in restaurants and tea houses, we can also see that in any social environment, Western orchestral music that can be regarded as folk music may have certain differences, but it must be shared among all members and classes, so that folk music can achieve the integration of social functions [10].

Therefore, in summary, the music evaluation standards adopted for Western orchestral music in the Western music system are not universal, and for different social types and Western orchestral music, there is no distinction between good and bad. Instead, Western orchestral music should be a form of expression that has profound cultural significance for every individual in the social environment at that time, symbolizing the characteristics and values of civilization throughout history. In a sense, it is also the cultural nature and characteristics exhibited by a portion of the population in the process of historical development.

6. Conclusion

For the improvisation components of Western orchestral music, we should pay sufficient attention to the commonalities and diversity that exist in them. In the face of commonalities, we should not directly apply the principles of Western music to our Western orchestral music. We need to grasp the characteristics and inherent structures between various systems based on the consideration of music structure. Under different social structures, there are also different environments and perspectives on music creation. Therefore, we should maintain an objective attitude towards the improvisation components of Western orchestral music, conduct in-depth research on the given and later added parts of its music construction, and integrate and integrate them with modern culture.

References

1. Huang Wei, Qiu Zhongzhi. Ecological analysis of ethnic music culture in promoting rural development [J]. *Art Review*, 2023 (24): 17-20
2. Yang Chenchen. Methods of inheriting ethnic music culture in music teaching in universities [J]. *Art Outlook*, 2023 (16): 130-132
3. Li Yue Research on Jia Xinfeng's "General Theory of Music Education" [D]. Yangzhou University, 2023. DOI: 10.27441/d.cnki.gyzdu.2023.002297
4. Fu Rong. The Basic Characteristics and Laws of Western Music Development from the Perspective of Mass Music [J]. *Voice of the Yellow River*, 2023 (09): 175-178. DOI: 10.19340/j.cnki.hhzs.2023.09.023
5. Oujixun Research on the Historical Formation and Application of Octave Scale [D]. Shanghai Conservatory of Music, 2023. DOI: 10.27319/d.cnki.gsyzy.2023.0000111
6. Niu Ruijie. Strategies for the Joint Development of College Music Teaching and Ethnic Music Culture Inheritance [J]. *Drama House*, 2023 (12): 97-99

7. Zhu Junyi. Research on the Inheritance of Ethnic Music Culture and the Industrialization of Art Resources [J]. Chinese Journal of Education, 2023 (04): 154
8. Zhang Xiaoxue On the Transformation of Sound Structure Force from Pitch to Tone Color in the Posttonal Period [D]. Shanghai Conservatory of Music, 2023. DOI: 10.27319/d.cnki.gsyty.2023.000109
9. Fan Xinyu. Exploring the Development Path of School Children's Ethnic Orchestras from the Perspective of Inheriting Ethnic Music Culture: Taking Tiantao Experimental School in Nanning as an Example [J]. China Music Education, 2023 (02): 18-22
10. Li Jieyuan. Exploration of the Development Ideas and Cultural Inheritance Approaches of Ethnic Music Education in Colleges and Universities: A Review of "Research on the Inheritance of Chinese Ethnic Music Culture and College Music Education" [J]. Chinese Journal of Education, 2023 (01): 149
11. Zhong Lijuan. Exploring the Value and Path of the Integration of College Music Education and Ethnic Music Culture [J]. The Road to Success, 2023 (01): 13-16
12. Wu Di. On the Inheritance and Development Strategies of Ethnic Music Culture in College Music Teaching [J]. Art Review, 2022 (23): 87-90+108
13. Liu Shuabing. Based on the Inheritance of Ethnic Music Culture - The Tradition and Modernity of Flute Performance Styles in Universities [J]. Art Review, 2022 (33): 42-44
14. Danjul, Bao Sultan. The Inheritance and Development of Ethnic Music Culture in Music Education and Teaching in Universities [J]. Research on Ethnic Higher Education, 2022, 10 (06): 82-86. DOI: 10.14045/j.cnki.rhen.2022.06.014
15. Gao Pingping. Research on the Ecology of Ethnic Music Culture in the Process of Rural Revitalization [J]. Journal of Shandong Agricultural Engineering College, 2022, 39 (10): 97-101. DOI: 10.15948/j.cnki.37-1500/s.2022.10.012
16. Wang Lihong. The Struggle and Integration of Nationalism and Modernity [D]. Guizhou University, 2022. DOI: 10.27047/d.cnki.ggudu.2022.002367
17. Zhao Zixun, Wang Xinyu. On the Teaching of Music in Universities and the Inheritance of Ethnic Music Culture [C]//The Intelligent Learning and Innovation Research Committee of the China Smart Engineering Research Association. Proceedings of the Nanning Forum on Education, Teaching and Management (2). Proceedings of the Nanning Forum on Education, Teaching and Management (2), 2022:242-247. DOI: 10.26914/c.cnkihy.2022.017104
18. Liu Jun. Exploration of Integrating Ethnic Music Culture into Higher Vocational Music Classrooms [J]. Journal of Hubei Open Vocational College, 2022,35 (07): 160-161
19. Wang Henghua. Research on the Development of Cross border Ethnic Music Culture between China and Vietnam [J]. Art Review, 2022 (06): 176-178
20. Zheng Xiaolu. Exploration of the Cultural Inheritance and Development of Ethnic Music Education in Universities in the Era of Science and Technology Informatization - Review of "Research on the Inheritance of Chinese Ethnic Music Culture and Music Education in Universities" [J]. People's Yangtze River, 2022,53 (03): 231
21. Wang Chang. An Analysis of the Inheritance and Development of Ethnic Music Culture in High School Music Classroom Teaching [J]. Chinese Literature and Art Journal, 2022 (03): 134-136
22. Zhao Yu, Zhang Luoxiao. The role of aesthetic values in popular music in the development of ethnic music culture [J]. Art Review, 2022 (08): 13-15
23. Zhou Yuan. Research on the Inheritance and Development of Minority Music Culture in the Northern Guangxi Region [J]. Guangxi Education, 2022 (06): 21-24
24. Tian Juanjuan. Exploration of the Inheritance and Innovative Development of Ethnic Music Culture [J]. Time Report (Benliu), 2022 (01): 73-75
25. Wang Chao. Developing Traditional Chinese Opera into Campus and Inheriting Ethnic Music Culture [J]. Drama House, 2021 (33): 59-60
26. Lin Hang. A Different Perspective in Rational Speculation: A Review of Ye Songrong's "Draft on the History of European Music Culture - European Music from the Perspective of Chinese People" [J]. Art Review, 2021 (03): 151-160. DOI: 10.16364/j.cnki.cn11-4907/j.2021.03.016
27. Wang Yong, Qiu Zihua. The Aesthetic Characteristics of the Original Ecological Nature of Eastern Music [J]. Journal of Huazhong Normal University (Humanities and Social Sciences Edition), 2021,60 (01): 106-110
28. Yu Danrui The National Discourse Debate on Chinese Art Criticism in the Post New Era [D]. Guizhou University, 2020. DOI: 10.27047/d.cnki.ggudu.2020.000726
29. Zang Heng Analysis of Traditional Cultural Thoughts in Chinese Modern and Contemporary Music Creation [D]. Nanjing Academy of Arts, 2019
30. Ye Jialiang A Study on Liszt's Piano Work "Travel Years" from the Perspective of Chinese "Virtual and Real" Theory [D]. Fujian Normal University, 2019. DOI: 10.27019/d.cnki.gfjsu.2019.000012
31. Liu Jiangxia A Study on Cultural Identity in Traditional Chinese Music Teaching [D]. Northeastern Normal University, 2019. DOI: 10.27011/d.cnki.gdbsu.2019.000214
32. Wang Xiaonan A Study on the Hundred Year Erhu Music Style and Cultural Identity [D]. Nanjing Academy of Arts, 2019
33. Wang Tingting Research on the Performance Space of Traditional Chinese Musical Instruments [D]. Xi'an University of Architecture and Technology, 2019. DOI: 10.27393/d.cnki.gxazu.2019.000023
34. Xu Yanting Returning to Home for New Development [D]. Nanjing Academy of Arts, 2018
35. Pan Lan. Emphasis on "Differentiation" Consciousness: Reflections on the Teaching of Western Music History in China from the Characteristics of Western "Postmodernism" [J]. People's Music, 2018 (04): 36-40

36. Chen Peigang Research on Multicultural Concepts and Teaching of Basic Music Courses in Normal Universities [D]. Nanjing Academy of Arts, 2017
37. Yuan Lijun. Exploration of the Artistic Characteristics and Teaching Models of Western Classical Music - Problems and Countermeasures in the Current Teaching of "Western Music Masterpieces" [J]. Ge Hai, 2016 (05): 46-51
38. Liu Di The Fusion of Modern Psychology and Western Philosophy of Music [D]. Nanchang University, 2016
39. Cui Jian. On the Artistic Charm of Traditional Mongolian Instrumental Music "Huo Bu Si". Northern Music, 2016, 36 (03): 17
40. Cui Jian. A Review of Traditional Ethnic Instrumental Music Creation - Taking the Mongolian plucked instrument Huobusi as an Example [J]. China Ethnic Expo, 2016 (01): 120-121
41. Cui Jian. Talking about the Current Situation and Preservation of Mongolian Instrumental Music 'Huo Bu Si' [J]. Northern Music, 2015, 35 (24): 12
42. Cui Jian. My Opinion on the Application of Innovative Teaching Methods for Ethnic Instrumental Music - Taking the Teaching Application of Mongolian Plucked Instrument Huobusi as an Example [J]. Music Time and Space, 2015 (20): 134-136+115
43. Cui Jian. Analysis of the Artistic Creation Characteristics and Concepts of Bayar Instrumental Music Works - Taking the Creation of Mongolian Plucked Instrument Huobusi and Accordion Works as Examples [J]. Music Time and Space, 2015 (19): 45-46+42
44. Wang Bin Deng Staple's New Music [D]. Xi'an Conservatory of Music, 2014
45. Li Ang Research on Schoenberg's "First Chamber Symphony" [D]. Shanghai Conservatory of Music, 2014